

Fundamental Rights and Horizontal Direct Effect under the Charter

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ABSTRACT

The effect of fundamental rights in private relationships is a controversial question not only within Member States, but also with regard to rights enshrined in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union. Recent ECJ Judgments have been read as adopting a stance in favour of recognizing horizontal direct effect to certain rights. This paper addresses the issue based on the understanding of fundamental rights as principles that impose upon public authorities an optimization command. This comprehension of fundamental rights is crucial to explain the need of a legislative intervention in order to ensure their enforceability in private relationships and, therefore, to conclude that the rights enshrined in the Charter do not have horizontal direct effect. Only exceptionally certain fundamental rights do not require this intervention because they are defined as such in the private sphere, and thus within the scope of private relationships. The same applies for human dignity, which is directly enforceable in private relationships since it is inextricable tied to the essence of human beings. As we will show, this view is consistent with the EU legislative action and ECJ case law.

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1. Opening Remarks

The horizontal direct effect of fundamental rights, i.e., whether they are binding on private relationships, thus being enforceable between private parties, has been extensively debated by national legal scholarship, mostly in mainland Europe. This debate evidences that there is no clear and unambiguous answer within Member States or domestic legal orders.¹ Therefore, there is neither an easy approach to the rights enshrined in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (CFREU or the “Charter”) under EU law.² As in many national Constitutions, the Charter lacks specific provisions in this regard but, admittedly, it fails to mention private parties as the addressees of these

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¹ Jarass (2016), pp. 33-34, confirming that this matter has barely been discussed in the United Kingdom and the United States.

² Lohsse, Schulze (2016), pp. 16-21.

fundamental rights provisions.³ The CFREU is worded as follows: “The provisions of this Charter are addressed to the institutions and bodies of the Union,” as well as to Member States when they implement EU law (Article 51(1) CFREU).⁴ Member States implement Union law when transposing Directives or enforcing EU law provisions through domestic pieces of legislation, but also when adopting any provisions or acts falling within the scope of EU law.⁵ At first, the wording of this provision suggests that the Charter intended to limit the effectiveness of the rights enshrined therein to subordinate or unequal relationships. Nonetheless, as recently declared by the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) in *Shimizu*:

“[...] it should be noted that, although Article 51(1) of the Charter states that the provisions thereof are addressed to the institutions, bodies, offices and agencies of the European Union with due regard for the principle of subsidiarity and to the Member States only when they are implementing EU law, Article 51(1) does not, however, address the question whether those individuals may, where appropriate, be directly required to comply with certain provisions of the Charter and cannot, accordingly, be interpreted as meaning that it would systematically preclude such a possibility.”⁶

The Court of Justice has also found that the principle of non-discrimination (Article 21 CFREU) and the right to paid annual leave (Article 31(2) CFREU) can be relied on by individuals in private relationships.

Indeed, both in *Bauer* and *Shimizu*, based on its previous case law, the CJEU points out that “the Court has, in particular, already held that the prohibition laid down in Article 21(1) of the Charter is sufficient in itself to confer on individuals a right which they may rely on as such in a dispute with another individual (Judgment of 17 April 2018, *Egenberger*, Case C-414/16, [...] paragraph 76), without, therefore, Article 51(1) of the Charter precluding it.”⁷ In *Cresco*, the Court asserted that “[t]he prohibition of all discrimination on grounds of religion or belief is mandatory as a general principle of EU law. That prohibition, which is laid down in Article 21(1) of the Charter, is sufficient in itself to confer on individuals a right which they may rely on as such in disputes between them in a field covered by EU law.”⁸ However, as shown below, these insights are not enough to conclude that fundamental rights enshrined in the Charter have a horizontal direct effect.

³ Lohsse, Schulze (2016), p. 22. As for the silence of Constitutions on the horizontal direct effect of fundamental rights, see Cruz Villalón (1988), p. 105.

⁴ This rule resembles other Member State constitutional provisions. See, for instance, Article 1(3) GG of the German Constitution (“*Die nachfolgenden Grundrechte binden Gesetzgebung, vollziehende Gewalt und Rechtsprechung als unmittelbar geltendes Recht*”), or Article 53(1) of the Spanish Constitution, which provides that “[t]he rights and freedoms recognised in Chapter 2 of the present Part are binding on all public authorities. Only by an act which in any case must respect their essential [core] content, could the exercise of such rights and freedoms be regulated, which shall be protected in accordance with the provisions of section 161(1)(a).”

⁵ Case C-617/10, *Åklagaren v. Hans Åkerberg Fransson*, Judgment of 26 February 2013, ECLI:EU:C:2013:105, paras. 45 and 46.

⁶ Case C-684/16, *Max-Planck-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der Wissenschaften eV v. T. Shimizu*, Judgment of 6 November 2018, ECLI:EU:C:2018:874, para. 76. Advocate General Cruz Villalón had already taken this stance in his opinion of 18 July 2013 in Case C-176/12, *Association de Médiation Sociale*, ECLI:EU:C:2013:491, paras. 28-35.

⁷ Joined Cases C-569/16 and C-570/16, *Stadt Wuppertal v. M.E. Bauer and V. Willmeroth v. M. Broßonn*, Judgment of 6 November 2018, ECLI:EU:C:2018:871, para. 89, and Case C-684/16, para. 78.

⁸ Case C-193/17, *Cresco Investigation GmbH v. Markus Achatzi*, Judgment of 22 January 2019, ECLI:EU:C:2019:43, para. 76.

This paper discusses the effectiveness of fundamental rights established in the Charter in private relationships. As shown below, these fundamental rights do not have a horizontal direct effect on a general basis. And they lack this effect because they qualify as *principles that impose upon public authorities*—not individuals—*an optimization command, which determines their application*. Based on this fundamental rights sketch, we will show that fundamental rights and freedoms granted to individuals in the Charter are only effective in private relationships to the extent determined by the relevant legislation (see sections 3.1 and 3.2). Thus, the judiciary should only apply and interpret these pieces of legislation on a case-by-case basis (see section 3.5 below). A different issue altogether is that certain fundamental rights could bring along such requirement or command also regarding private relationships (see section 2). Furthermore, human dignity—which is inextricably tied to the essence of human being—can be directly enforced within the scope of private relations (see section 3.4). Accordingly, to the extent that fundamental rights must be construed as optimization commands vis-à-vis public authorities that require a legislative expression to render them applicable to private relationships, they are not, by themselves, a limit to private or personal autonomy, which is an expression of free will (see section 4 below).

2. What Type of Norms Are Fundamental Rights?

In order to examine the horizontal direct effect of fundamental rights, it is worth determining *what type of norms they are*. As aptly pointed out by Alexy, fundamental rights are principles, not rules.⁹ Principles are norms commanding that something be performed to the highest degree. Thus, fundamental rights can be defined as *optimization commands* for certain legal content from which rights can be inferred vis-à-vis public authorities, given that such commands are addressed to public authorities.¹⁰ This definition covers both fundamental rights from domestic legal orders and those enshrined in the Charter. There are no grounds to construe the latter otherwise. In contrast with fundamental rights, other provisions—such as “principles” within the meaning of Article 52(5) CFREU—do not provide for such a command. Rather, they require legislative measures to implement them and further define their substance. Therefore, they do not give rise to individual rights vis-à-vis public authorities.¹¹ Within the scope of the Charter, the following qualify as “principles:” the rights of the elderly (Article 25 CFREU); integration of persons with disabilities (Article 26 CFREU); workers’ right to information and consultation within the undertaking (Article 27 CFREU); the right to protection in the event of unjustified or unfair dismissal (Article 30 CFREU); the right of access to health care (Article 35 CFREU); the right of access to services of general economic interest (Article 36 CFREU); environmental protection (Article 37 CFREU), and consumer protection (Article 38 CFREU).¹²

⁹ See Alexy (1993), pp. 81-82.

¹⁰ Ibid, pp. 140-141.

¹¹ Menéndez (2004), pp. 161-166. Consequently, out of the list of rights and principles laid down in the Charter, only those providing for optimization commands giving rise to individual rights vis-à-vis public authorities qualify as fundamental rights. Any rights and principles whose content depends on a specific legislative expression, whether by the EU or national legislatures, will not be considered as fundamental rights. Ibid, pp. 179 and 182-183. See also Case C-176/12, Association de Médiation Sociale, Judgment of 15 January 2014, ECLI:EU:C:2014:2, paras. 44-48.

¹² Ibid, pp. 182-183 and Lohsse, Schulze (2016), p. 23. Regarding workers’ right to information and consultation (Article 27 CFREU), see the Opinion by AG Cruz Villalón in Case C-176/12, paras. 51-53,

These principles provide for “more open-ended” commands, so they cannot give rise to individual rights. They must be implemented by acts of the European Union or the Member States. “Those implementing acts must be understood as acts necessary to give specific legislative expression to a ‘principle’ and having no other purpose than that of providing it with sufficient substance for it to attain substantive independence and, ultimately, become a judicially cognisable right.”¹³ Certainly, these provisions do not suffice to confer individual rights which may be invoked as such¹⁴. However, this does not preclude that they be used as interpretative and validity criteria for the courts and tribunals (see Article 52(5) CFREU).¹⁵

The distinct element of this definition of fundamental rights is that, as opposed to rules, there is no such thing as fulfilment or non-fulfilment.¹⁶ Fundamental rights provide *prima facie* reasons and lay down *prima facie* commands, i.e., non-definitive requirements or commands.¹⁷ Therefore, fundamental rights cannot be generally considered to prevail over each other no matter what. The transition from a *prima facie* right to a final or definitive right—which entails acknowledging that an individual is entitled to something—is subject to an *assessment of preference*.¹⁸ This has a direct implication for any conflicts between fundamental rights in a given case. These fundamental rights clashes must be solved determining which right “outweighs” the other. *This is not a matter of validity, but a matter of balancing*.¹⁹

Insofar as this optimization command embedded in fundamental rights targets public authorities, it goes without saying that fundamental rights entail freedom and equality safeguards vis-à-vis public authorities.²⁰ On the one hand, fundamental rights ban any intervention or interference by public authorities (a *prohibition to intervene* or *Abwehrssverbot*) with their scope of freedom. Simultaneously, on the other hand, fundamental rights give rise to a *right to protection*, thereby imposing upon public authorities a duty to protect individuals in their relations with others (*Schutzgebot*).²¹ In

and Judgment of 15 January 2014, Association de Médiation Sociale, ECLI:EU:C:2014:2, paras. 45-48. As for the right to paid annual leave (Article 31(2) CFREU), which had been listed as a principle by several scholars, see Joined Cases C-569/16 and C-570/16, para. 58, where the Court defines it as a fundamental right only requiring that lawmakers determine its exact duration. In this vein, see also Case C-684/16, para. 74.

¹³ Opinion delivered by AG Cruz Villalón in Case C-176/12, para 62.

¹⁴ Case C-176/12, para 47.

¹⁵ For further detail, see the Opinion delivered by AG Cruz Villalón in Case C-176/12, paras. 61-71. In these terms, this principle may be relied on in disputes between individuals (see, paras. 38-42). Also, see the scholarly work by Mangas (2008a), p. 819.

¹⁶ Alexy (1993), pp. 86-87. Díez-Picazo Giménez (2013), Chapter 1, pp. 11-12, specifies that certain Spanish Constitution fundamental rights (*Constitución Española*, CE) are structured as rules, such as those set out in Article 17 CE— “[...] the person arrested must be set free or handed over to the judicial authorities within a maximum period of seventy two hours” or in Article 18 CE—“no entry or search may be made without the consent of the householder or a legal warrant, except in cases of *flagrante delicto*.” Regarding EU law, Menéndez (2004), ARENA Report 9: p. 184 acknowledges that a fundamental right can contain a principle and a rule at the same time.

¹⁷ Alexy (1993), pp. 99-103. Although principles are sometimes reinforced by arguing in their favour, they do not quite become rules.

¹⁸ *Ibid*, pp. 102-103.

¹⁹ *Ibid*, pp. 89-90. See Díez-Picazo Giménez (2013), Chapter 1, pp. 11-12.

²⁰ Starck (2002), *Revista Española de Derecho Constitucional* 66: pp. 70 and 72.

²¹ On the twofold dimension of fundamental rights as “prohibitions to intervene” (*Abwehrssverbot*) and “duties of protection” (*Schutzgebot*), see Canaris (1984), pp. 212-213 and 225-226, and Alfaro (1993), pp. 66, 69-70. On the individual right to protection, see Alexy (1993), pp. 435 and 437. In fact, Canaris notes,

this regard, “[o]nly the individualization [or ‘subjectivization’] of rights to protection accurately reflects the ‘original and everlasting meaning of fundamental rights’ as individual rights.”²² Public authorities are thus forced to implement specific legislative and regulatory initiatives and to take specific action, in order to define the legal scope or legal spheres of these right holders whilst drawing appropriate boundaries between them.²³ Note that fundamental rights holders being entitled to a right to protection by public authorities does not specifically impose on the state how to afford such protection. Since fundamental rights are essentially optimization commands, they require the greatest protection to the extent actually and legally possible.²⁴ Under these circumstances, public authorities—and legislators in particular (see section 3 below)—are free to choose the most suitable means to maximize the fundamental rights at stake, although ensuring the effectiveness thereof.²⁵

*Exceptionally, there are fundamental rights defined as such in the private sphere, and thus within the scope of private relationships.*²⁶ See for instance, gender equality in marriage (Article 32(1) CE), or equal pay (Article 23(1) CFREU).²⁷ These rights are somewhat in line with the so-called “two-way rights” (*derechos bidireccionales*), meaning that they are not only granted vis-à-vis public authorities, but also with respect to private parties.²⁸ The key to determine the effectiveness of these rights in private relationships is not the legal interest involved, but rather the *sphere where these rights are granted*. If certain fundamental rights are acknowledged within private relationships—for example, in unequal or subordinate relationships like employer-employee relationships, where trade union freedom or collective bargaining apply—, they will be effective between private parties.²⁹ The effectiveness of these rights in private law relations is therefore immediate due to the right’s structure.³⁰ To this end, the protected legal interest and its ties to private law are not significant by themselves. No matter how intense the connection between the right to private property with private law may be, the right to property (Article 17(1) CFREU) still targets public authorities, who may only

ibid, 225-226, that one of public authorities’ (or the state’s) primary duties is to protect individuals from other individuals. See also, von Münch (1997), pp. 46-48, who points out as purpose for fundamental rights: imposing on public authorities a “public duty of protection.” Concerning the Charter, in this connection, see Mangas (2008a), p. 819.

²² Alexy (1993), pp. 439-440.

²³ Alexy (1993), pp. 435 and 446. Along these lines, see the Opinion of AG Cruz Villalón in Case C-176/12, para. 36.

²⁴ Ibid, p. 448.

²⁵ Ibid, pp. 446-448. This is why Fornasier (2015), p. 34, considers that this way of applying fundamental rights to private relations broadens the regulatory options for lawmakers than merely imposing them directly.

²⁶ Alfaro (2015a), p. 2. See also Cruz Villalón (2017), p. 112, referring to fundamental rights “to be exercised within the firm.”

²⁷ In the scholarly literature, regarding gender equality in marriage, see Starck (2002), pp. 71-72. He considers also included in this category trade union freedom. See also Alfaro (2015a), pp. 1 and 4, on equal pay. The right to paid annual leave is considered effective in private relationships within firms (see Cases C-569/16 and C-570/16, para. 90; see also Case C-684/16, para. 79). In this regard, the Court of Justice states that it entails “[...] by its very nature, a corresponding obligation on the employer, which is to grant such periods of paid leave.”

²⁸ This notion is taken from Cruz Villalón (1988), pp. 106-107. Let us recall that “two-way rights” is a broader category, encompassing freedom of expression, freedom of association (including its negative dimension, the right to decline membership) or freedom of assembly; these rights and freedoms may not be addressed to private parties after all.

²⁹ Lohsse, Schulze (2016), p. 19. According to them, there is no need to resort to the *Drittwirkung* in these cases.

³⁰ Ibid, p. 16.

take citizens' property on grounds of "public utility" and upon payment of fair compensation.³¹ When fundamental rights are not granted within private relationships, regardless of the legal interest at stake and its connection with private law, as shown below, they will be as effective between private parties as determined by lawmakers.

3. Fundamental Rights in Private Relationships

3.1. Optimization Command and Legislative Action

The approach to fundamental rights discussed above determines their effectiveness in private relationships. Defined as optimization commands addressed to public authorities, fundamental rights can have no effect in private relationships, because they do not allow to establish guiding criteria to govern private-private relations or to limit individuals' behaviour towards their counterparts. Legislative action is required, balancing the rights at stake, in order for fundamental rights to fulfil this purpose. Otherwise, an individual entitled to a fundamental right could interfere with another fundamental right holder's freedom. Note that this outcome would be to contrary to some national Constitutions – *i.e.*, the Spanish Constitution (CE), which provides, on the one hand, that "the inviolable rights [...] inherent" to every individual, alongside "the respect for the law and for the rights of others," are "the foundation of political order and social peace" (Article 10(1) CE), and on the other hand, that [o]nly by an act which in any case must respect their essential [core] content, could the exercise of such rights and freedoms be regulated" (Article 53(1) (CE)). Furthermore, it would be incompatible with the Charter, which in the same vein, provides that "[a]ny limitation on the exercise of the rights and freedoms recognised by this Charter must be provided for by law and respect the essence of those rights and freedoms" (Article 52(1) CFREU).³²

Thus, in order for fundamental rights to be effective in private relationships, they need a legislative expression, *i.e.*, legislative measures, or legislative action, to implement them.³³ As discussed before (see section 2 above), fundamental rights that have been granted within private relationships are an exception to this. It is worth examining how legislators fulfil this duty of protection regarding *conflicts between fundamental rights*, *i.e.*, cases where fundamental rights granted to an individual clash with others (*inter alia*, the well-known clashes between freedom of expression and the rights to honour and privacy). Enforcing certain fundamental rights in private relations can ultimately restrict other rights, thereby overstepping and limiting the right holder's sphere of freedom.³⁴ Therefore, lawmakers should determine the "social enforceability" of fundamental rights.³⁵ At this point, it is worth emphasizing the importance of understanding that fundamental rights are optimization commands or, in other words, principles (i) that can be fulfilled to varying degrees, having regard to what is actually and legally possible in each case, and (ii) that should be fulfilled to the greatest extent possible (see section 2

³¹ However, Beladiez (2017), pp. 92-93, considers that the key is the protected legal interest, and it subsequently specifies that their scope depends on the type of legal relationship where they are exercised.

³² Regarding Spanish law, see Alfaro (1993), p. 69. With regard to the Charter, see Menéndez (2004), p. 180.

³³ Alfaro (2017), p. 5.

³⁴ Díez-Picazo Giménez (2012), pp. 148-149. See, among other German scholarly works, Hesse (2011), p. 172.

³⁵ Alfaro (1993), p. 73.

above). Therefore, we need lawmakers to take action in order to maximize “the amount of fundamental right” that should be acknowledged within private relationships in the event of clashes with other fundamental rights.³⁶ Indeed, legislators are in the best position to do this, since they can take into account all the elements and interests at stake to solve any conflicts between fundamental rights. It is not for the judiciary to strike the aforesaid balance, but (i) to enforce it on a case-by-case basis and, where appropriate, (ii) to ensure that lawmaking and the courts’ interpretation and adjudication fulfils the duty of protection entailed by the fundamental rights at stake (see section 3.4 below).

Lawmakers try to strike a fair balance by preventing registration of distinctive signs contrary to the right of honour or human dignity in spite that free enterprise (the freedom to conduct a business) and freedom of expression are at stake—see Article 7(1)(f) of the EU Trademark Regulation, preventing registration of trademarks or distinctive signs contrary to public policy or to accepted principles of morality.³⁷

The foregoing does not mean that it rests on legislators to grant or acknowledge fundamental rights. In these cases, legislators are not acknowledging a right, but rather turning it into positive statutory private law, thereby defining its scope in its interactions with other rights. Within EU law, this task has been entrusted to the legislator, who must now draft the provisions defining the said scope of conflicting rights balancing all duties of protection in order to preserve the rights’ essence (see Article 52(1) CFREU).³⁸ As noted above, legislators are in the best position to do this, since they can take into account all the elements and interests involved. Legislators hereby ensures social peace, preventing private parties from determining the scope of conflicting rights on their own. Perhaps, that is why it has been authoritatively held that “*Drittwirkung* should be left to lawmakers.”³⁹

This approach to the effectiveness of fundamental rights does not undermine their fundamental nature. They remain “fundamental,” regardless if they are deemed to have horizontal direct effect. Fundamental rights qualify as fundamental because, by imposing an optimization command on public authorities, they are binding on public authorities’ legal decision-making.⁴⁰ Accordingly, they are granted or acknowledged regardless of legislators. They stem from the Constitution—or the Charter, within EU law—and they are subsequently enforced upon public authorities. If a given legislature passes a legal provision, whether a public or private law rule, it must ensure compliance with, and the protection of, fundamental rights. Hence, fundamental rights have an impact on various legal domains through this lawmaking activity, obviously including private law. Private law thus becomes an additional instrument—like criminal law, for instance—to shape the

³⁶ Alexy (1993), pp. 86-87. See also, Paz-Ares, Alfaro (2003), pp. 5972-5973. This explains why the “legislative action” and the fundamental right enshrined in the Charter are not identical. In a similar vein, see Fornasier (2015), p. 45.

³⁷ As repeatedly noted by the General Court, the grounds for refusal of registration of trademarks contrary to public policy provided in Article 7(1)(f) of the EU Trademark Regulation are intended to preserve social and democratic values preventing signs contrary to core EU values, such as human dignity, integrity and individual freedom (Arts. 2, 3 and 6 CFREU), from being registered as EU trademarks. This was the case with “La mafia se sienta a la mesa”, referring to a criminal organization originating in Italy, or “Paki”, which in English is considered a racial slur. In this regard, Cases T-526/09 (PAKI), Judgment of 5 October 2011, ECLI:EU:T:2011:564, para. 15, and T-1/17 (LA MAFIA SE SIENTA A LA MESA), Judgment of 15 March 2018, ECLI:EU:T:2018:146, para. 36.

³⁸ Menéndez (2004), pp. 179-180.

³⁹ Cruz Villalón (1988), p. 113. In a similar vein, see Jarass (2016), pp. 50-51.

⁴⁰ Menéndez (2004), pp. 177-179.

duty of protection imposed on lawmakers by fundamental rights.⁴¹ But this legislative action aimed at fulfilling the aforesaid duty of protection also evidences the noticeable impact of fundamental rights on private lawmaking.⁴²

3.2. *Legislative Action in EU Law*

Lawmakers must balance the fundamental rights laid down in the CFREU to determine their effectiveness in private relationships, as stated in many Court of Justice rulings.⁴³ Consider, for example, the Court’s decision in *Promusicae*. This case involved a conflict between the right to property and the right to an effective remedy, on the one hand, and the right to privacy, on the other. In response to the request for a preliminary ruling, the Court found that it is for the EU legislator—as well as for domestic legislatures—to strike a balance between competing fundamental rights through EU Directives and domestic provisions transposing or implementing them:

“The mechanisms allowing those different rights and interests to be balanced are contained, first, in Directive 2002/58 itself, in that it provides for rules which determine in what circumstances and to what extent the processing of personal data is lawful and what safeguards must be provided for, and in the three Directives mentioned by the national court, which reserve the cases in which the measures adopted to protect the rights they regulate affect the protection of personal data. Second, they result from the adoption by the Member States of national provisions transposing those Directives and their application by the national authorities. [...]

That being so, the Member States must, when transposing the Directives mentioned above, take care to rely on an interpretation of the Directives which allows a fair balance to be struck between the various fundamental rights protected by the Community legal order.”⁴⁴

⁴¹ Canaris (1984), p. 227. See also, Hesse (1995), p. 60: “In case of conflicts, civil law faces a daunting challenge: it must find, by itself, the way and the extent of fundamental rights’ influence by balancing the fundamental rights at stake.” Ibid, pp. 62-63.

⁴² In this connection, see Díez-Picazo Giménez (2012), p. 148. His interpretation being that, in this case, private law is directly affected by fundamental rights, which impact any provision, Alfaro (1993), pp. 71 and 76. Among German scholarly work, see Lohsse, Schulze (2016), pp. 24-25. Nevertheless, this should not be regarded as a “constitutionalization” of private law or as the subordination thereof to constitutional law. However, see Cherednychenko (2007), p. 142.

⁴³ In this vein, see Starke (2016), p. 219.

⁴⁴ Case C-275/06, *Promusicae v. Telefónica de España*, SAU, Judgment of 29 January 2008, ECLI:EU:C:2008:54, paras. 66 and 68. This line of reasoning can be found in other rulings. See Case C-314/12, *UPC Telekabel Wien GmbH v. Constantin Film Verleih GmbH*, Judgment of 27 March 2014, ECLI:EU:C:2014:192, para. 46, within the framework of Directive 2001/29, on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society. The case involved a conflict between the right to property—namely intellectual property—and the freedom to conduct a business. See also Case C-70/10, *Scarlet Extended SA v. Société belge des auteurs, compositeurs et éditeurs SCRL (SABAM)*, Judgment of 24 November 2011, ECLI:EU:C:2011:771, paras. 44-46, within the framework of a number of Directives, related, essentially, with the protection of copyright and privacy, as well as with the processing of personal data. The Court stresses the need to balance the right to property against other fundamental rights at stake, such as the freedom to conduct a business, the right to privacy and freedom of information. In Case C-580/13, *Coty German GmbH v. Stadtsparkasse Magdeburg*, Judgment of 16 June 2015, ECLI:EU:C:2015:485, paras. 34-43, the Court assessed the compatibility with Directive 2004/48, on the enforcement of intellectual property rights, of a domestic provision on banking secrecy allowing to deny access to banking information of a private party that was selling counterfeit perfumes online. The Court found that this provision disregarded the balance achieved by the EU legislator in the

Therefore, this case should not be deemed as an example of the “irradiation effect” that fundamental rights would have on private relationships—if there was no prior balancing by legislators—and which would require to interpret any national provisions implementing EU Directives in the light of fundamental rights.⁴⁵ Conversely, in this case, the Court of Justice clearly states that (i) the EU legislator has balanced the fundamental rights at stake in the set of abovementioned Directives, and (ii) the implementing or transposing domestic provisions must abide by, or ensure, the “fair balance between the various competing fundamental rights” struck by such Directives.⁴⁶

Indeed, the Court has further specified that balancing the fundamental rights at issue (and thus fulfilling the duty of protection imposed by fundamental rights on legislators) is not only for the EU legislator, but also for national legislatures. It did so in *Lindqvist*. The case involved a conflict between Mrs Lindqvist’s freedom of expression as a catechist, and the right to privacy and data protection of the individuals whose information she posted on her website. The Court found that:

“The mechanisms allowing those different rights and interests to be balanced are contained, first, in Directive 95/46 itself, in that it provides for rules which determine in what circumstances and to what extent the processing of personal data is lawful and what safeguards must be provided for. Second, they result from the adoption, by the Member States, of national provisions implementing that Directive and their application by the national authorities.”⁴⁷

From this standpoint, the CJEU ruling in *Egenberger* should neither be considered an expression of fundamental rights’ horizontal direct effect.⁴⁸ The facts of the case evidence that there was a conflict between fundamental rights: on the one hand, the German Evangelical Church’s religious freedom, construed as the freedom to make decisions based on their ethos (Article 10 CFREU); on the other, the principle of non-discrimination on grounds of religion suffered by a potential worker who was ultimately excluded in a recruitment procedure for not having any specific religious beliefs (Article 21 CFREU) and the right to an effective remedy (Article 47 CFREU). This conflict should have been solved by applying a national provision—the *Allgemeines Gleichbehandlungsgesetz*, AGG (German General Act on Equal Treatment)—transposing Directive 2000/78 establishing a general framework for equal treatment in employment and occupation.⁴⁹ This Directive expressly declares its purpose (i.e., to define the scope of the principle of non-discrimination on grounds of religion, *inter alia*, within employment relationships). And, as confirmed by the Court of Justice, the purpose of the relevant domestic provisions is to prevent and eliminate all forms of discrimination, including any discrimination on the grounds of religion or belief.⁵⁰ In the words of the

abovementioned Directive between property rights—tied to intellectual property rights in particular—and effective legal protection, on the one hand, and the processing of personal data, on the other.

⁴⁵ Jarass (2016), § 51 RdN 32, considers that this is the Court of Justice’s approach.

⁴⁶ Hesse speaks about “balancing or weighing.” See footnote 41 above.

⁴⁷ Case C-101/01, *Bodil Lindqvist*, ECLI:EU:C:2003:596, Judgment of 6 November 2003, para. 82.

⁴⁸ Case C-414/16, *Vera Egenberger v. Evangelisches Werk für Diakonie und Entwicklung eV*, Judgment of 17 April 2018, ECLI:EU:C:2018:257. However, Colombi (2019), pp. 294-305 considers that it is a paramount example of horizontal direct effect. See also, Azpitarte (2019), p. 1575.

⁴⁹ Council Directive 2000/78/EC, of 27 November 2000, establishing a general framework for equal treatment in employment and occupation (OJ 2000, L 303, p. 16).

⁵⁰ “The purpose of this Directive is to lay down a general framework for combating discrimination on the grounds of religion or belief [...] with a view to putting into effect in the Member States the principle of equal treatment” (Article 1).

CJEU, Article 4(2) of the Directive (to which the Court devotes most of its interpretative efforts) “sets out the criteria to be taken into account in the balancing exercise which must be performed in order to ensure a fair balance between those competing fundamental rights.”⁵¹ Self-evidently, the application of the fundamental rights at stake in this case relies on the balance struck by the EU legislator in the Directive. As shown above, national legislators must abide by this balance when transposing the EU Directive into the national legal order.

There could be two main objections to this. First, one could claim that in the case at hand the Court of Justice has been forced to apply the right to an effective remedy directly (Article 47 CFREU) to make up for the misimplementation of the Directive. Second, that, based on the rights set out in the Charter, the Court has considered that domestic courts and tribunals should set aside a national provision contrary to the Charter rights. Both objections are untenable. As for the right to an effective remedy, the CJEU found that the evangelical church’s decision to exclude the candidate with no “confessional faith” had to be subject to judicial review, in order to assess whether such decision fulfilled the criteria laid down in the Directive enabling the coexistence of fundamental rights. Nevertheless, this cannot be construed as meaning that the right to an effective remedy had a direct effect in this private relationship. In fact, this need for judicial review is put into effect through two Directive provisions (Articles 9 and 10). The national legislator was required to implement these two provisions into national legislation, yet he failed to do so.⁵² *The Court is thus confirming the misimplementation—or, better said, the defective transposition—of the Directive into national law, which breaches the duty of protection of the fundamental rights at stake (inter alia, the right to an effective remedy).* And, as pointed out before, the Charter imposes this duty of protection both on EU and national legislators. This is precisely what allows to explain how fundamental rights act “as a palliative” for the lack of horizontal direct effect of Directives, once it becomes impossible to interpret national provisions in a manner consistent with EU law (i.e., disapplying any contrary provision of national legislation or setting aside incompatible national case law).⁵³ Nevertheless, it should not be construed as an example of the right’s horizontal direct effect.⁵⁴

Additionally, in response to the third question—whether a national provision that cannot be interpreted in conformity with the Directive can be set aside—the Court raises the mandatory nature of fundamental rights and the possibility that individuals can rely on an individual right in court. The Court’s line of reasoning does not contradict our approach to the horizontal direct effect of fundamental rights. Our stance is consistent with the claim that Articles 21 and 47 CFREU are “sufficient in itself [themselves] and does [do] not need to be made more specific by provisions of EU or national law to confer on individuals a right which they may rely on as such.”⁵⁵ Along with the “guarantee of

⁵¹ Case C-414/16, para. 52.

⁵² In this connection, see Case C-414/16, paras. 48, 49, 54 and 59. The same line of reasoning can be found in Case C-68/17, IR v. JQ, Judgment of 11 September 2018, ECLI:EU:C:2018:696, paras. 43-45.

⁵³ With regard to this “palliative role,” see the Opinion of AG Y. Bot of 25 November 2015, Case C-441/14, Dansk Industri v. Estate of Karsten Eigil Rasmussen, ECLI:EU:C:2015:776, para. 47. Consequently, the Court of Justice found that the application of a national provision which was contrary to principle of non-discrimination on grounds of age, “as given concrete expression” in Directive 2000/78, must be precluded in disputes among private persons (see Judgment 19 April 2016, ECLI:EU:C:2016:278, para. 27).

⁵⁴ In contrast, see Azpitarte (2019), p. 1572.

⁵⁵ Case C-414/16, paras. 76-78 and Case C-68/17, para. 69. Regarding the non-discrimination principle, this line of reasoning can also be found in Case C-193/17, para. 76.

non-interference,” fundamental rights entail a duty of protection for right holders vis-à-vis public authorities (see section 2 above). In the case at issue, fundamental right holders may consider that national legislators have disregarded such duty of protection when transposing the Directive that struck a balance between fundamental rights. If so, these right holders may seek that the competent courts interpret the national provision in conformity with the EU Directive—within the limits set out by CJEU case law⁵⁶— so that it fulfils such duty of protection (see section 3.5 below). Ultimately, as a branch of the state, a national court “would be required to secure *within its jurisdiction* the judicial protection for individuals flowing from Articles 21 and 47 of the Charter, and to guarantee the full effectiveness of those articles by disapplying if need be any contrary provision of national law.”⁵⁷ Based on such consistent interpretation, it is understandable that the Court of Justice enables the domestic court, when hearing the case, (i) *to depart from settled national case law* (stating that, where the church differentiates between activities “close to” and activities “remote from” proclamation of the church’s message, courts should not review whether that distinction is justified); and (ii) *to set aside the interpretation of the provision contrary to the Directive including the EU legislator’s balance between the fundamental rights at stake*.⁵⁸ The CJEU already did this in *Mangold* and *Kücükdeveci*, urging the national court to disapply certain domestic provisions that had not been amended by the legislator when implementing Directive 2000/78, in order to guarantee the full effectiveness of the general principle of non-discrimination in respect of age as implemented in the Directive.⁵⁹ Having set aside the case law or specific provision incompatible with EU law, *the competent domestic court should rule on the case, applying and interpreting any applicable national law provisions that are in conformity with the balance struck by the EU legislator* to ensure the optimization of the fundamental rights involved as determined in the Directive.⁶⁰ In accordance with well-known case law, we must rule out the possibility of directly applying the Directive striking the balance⁶¹.

One could argue that in *Cresco* the Court got a little closer to acknowledging the principle of non-discrimination’s horizontal direct effect.⁶² However, this ruling still applies prior case law. In this case, the Court examines an exception to the principle of non-discrimination on the grounds of religion provided by the Austrian legislator. In particular, it involves a piece of legislation granting the right to a public holiday on Good Friday only to employees who are members of certain Christian churches. The Court found a direct discrimination under Article 2 of Directive 2000/78. Such discrimination was deemed unreasonable for the protection of freedom of religion of employees favoured

⁵⁶ Case C-176/12, paras. 38-39, preventing an interpretation of national law *contra legem*. Likewise, Case C-193/17, para. 74.

⁵⁷ Case C-414/16, para. 79.

⁵⁸ Case C-414/16, paras. 72-73 and 81-82. See also, Case C-68/17, paras. 64-65 and 70-71, along with Case C-684/16, p. 60.

⁵⁹ Case C-144/04, *Werner Mangold v. Rüdiger Helm*, Judgment of 22 November 2005, ECLI:EU:C:2005:709, paras. 74-78, and Case C-555/07, *Seda Küçükdeveci v. Swedex GmbH & Co. KG*, Judgment of 19 January 2010, ECLI:EU:C:2010:21, paras. 53-56. In line with the body, see Fornasier (2015), p. 44.

⁶⁰ In this connection, see Case C-282/10, *Maribel Domínguez v. Centre Informatique du Centre Ouest Atlantique*, Judgment of 24 January 2012, ECLI:EU:C:2012:33, para. 27. On this aspect, among the scholars, see Alfaro (2015a), p. 6.

⁶¹ Case C-555/07, para. 46 and Case C-282/10, para. 37.

⁶² “Therefore, if it proved to be the case that national provisions could not be interpreted in a manner which was consistent with Directive 2000/78, the referring court would nevertheless be obliged to guarantee individuals the legal protection afforded to employees under Article 21 of the Charter and to guarantee the full effect of that article.”

by this measure (Article 5 of Directive 2000/78), since it cannot be considered necessary, there being alternative measures allowing to safeguard the said fundamental right.⁶³ As a result, based on the principle of non-discrimination, the Court ruled that “[i]n such a situation, a national court must set aside any discriminatory provision of national law, without having to request or await its prior removal by the legislature, and must apply to members of the disadvantaged group the same arrangements as those enjoyed by the persons in the other category.” Note that the Court backed up its line of reasoning with earlier case law.⁶⁴ According to that case law, the consistent interpretation requirement allows for setting aside the provision that is unreasonable in the light of the Directive. After disapplying the discriminatory restriction—i.e., granting the right to a holiday on Good Friday only to employees affiliated to certain churches—persons within the disadvantaged category will be afforded the same advantages as those enjoyed by persons within the favoured category.⁶⁵ Self-evidently, the non-discrimination principle has no horizontal direct effect in this case. Rather, *national law is once again interpreted in conformity with Directive 2000/78, which enforces the principle of non-discrimination in private relationships*. By setting aside the discriminatory restriction—granting the right to a public holiday on Good Friday only to employees who are members of certain churches—, the interpreting court is entitled to extend the favoured category to any individual as long as the legislator does not provide for a new non-discriminatory provision.

Fundamental rights intended to be effective within the private sphere (see section 2 above) pose a different issue altogether. *Bauer* and *Shimizu* aptly exemplify this. It is thus understandable that the Court of Justice makes the following statement:

“[T]he national court, before which a dispute between the legal heir of a deceased worker and the former employer of that worker has been brought, must disapply that national legislation and ensure that the legal heir receives payment from the employer of an allowance in lieu of paid annual leave acquired under those provisions and not taken by the worker before his death. That obligation on the national court is dictated by Article 7 of Directive 2003/88 and Article 31(2) of the Charter where the dispute is between the legal heir and an employer which has the status of a public authority, and under the second of those provisions where the dispute is between the legal heir and an employer who is a private individual” (emphasis added).⁶⁶

Before the Charter entered into force, the Court of Justice had reached a similar conclusion with regard to the principle of equal pay. In *Defrenne*, the CJEU found that Article 157 TFEU (ex Article 141 TEC)—requiring Member States to “ensure that the principle of equal pay for male and female workers for equal work or work of equal value [be] applied”—was a mandatory provision thus enforceable in contracts between individuals.⁶⁷ By doing so, the Court of Justice implemented this fundamental right through a specific mandatory provision, such as a Treaty provision (now Article 157 TFEU) from which it can be inferred a clear and unambiguous obligation in the field of

⁶³ Case C-193/17, paras. 60-61 and 67-68.

⁶⁴ Case C-193/17, para. 80.

⁶⁵ Case C-406/15, *Milkova*, Judgment of 9 March 2017, ECLI:EU:C:2017:198, paras. 66-69 and cited case law.

⁶⁶ Case C-569/16 and C-570/16, para. 92. See also, Case C-684/16, para. 81.

⁶⁷ Case C-43/75, *Gabrielle Defrenne v. Sabena*, Judgment of 8 April 1976, ECLI:EU:C:1976:56, para. 39. In this regard, see *Sarmiento* (2017), p. 4.

employment on which individuals can rely before national courts.⁶⁸ The Court of Justice hence declared the following:

“since [the relevant provision] is mandatory in nature, the prohibition on discrimination between men and women applies not only to the action of public authorities, but also extends to all agreements which are intended to regulate paid labour collectively, as well as to contracts between individuals.”⁶⁹

Once this fundamental right is set out in Article 23 CFREU and defined as a right effective in private relationships, individuals may directly rely on it without prejudice to any further specification or implementation by Article 157 TFEU.⁷⁰

3.3. Fundamental Rights and Freedoms of Movement

There could be a new argument against the previous analysis of the effect of fundamental rights in private law relationships, based on the effectiveness of freedoms of movement. Indeed, the Court of Justice has found that EU freedoms have a horizontal direct effect under certain circumstances.⁷¹ One could argue that there is no reason why fundamental rights should not be granted this effect. However, this view cannot be shared. Admittedly, just like fundamental rights, these freedoms are addressed to Member States.⁷² Ultimately, it is Member States who may somehow create obstacles to the free movement of production factors.⁷³ Nonetheless, this conclusion does not apply to fundamental rights for two reasons. Firstly, the so-called market access freedoms are not generally effective in private relationships. They are intended to ensure that market participants can access the market, which does not depend on private parties, but on Member States, who are actually able to prevent or remove entry barriers to guarantee that participants from other states can enter the market. As is the case with fundamental rights, the application of access freedoms to private law relations requires specific legislative action (for instance, by means of competition law).⁷⁴ Secondly, and more importantly, the CJEU has acknowledged that freedoms of movement are only horizontally effective under very specific circumstances. This clarification by the Court has been originally made when enforcing the prohibition of discrimination on grounds of nationality (Article 21(2) CFREU).⁷⁵ In this case, freedoms of movement are actually implementing the principle of non-discrimination on grounds of nationality,⁷⁶ thereby embodying such principle in primary law which, as is well-known, has direct effect. Therefore, based on this “legislative” action through the Treaties, individuals can directly rely on EU freedoms, not only vis-à-vis public authorities, but also in private relationships as an implementation of the aforementioned principle. Accordingly, horizontal direct effect of freedoms of movement does not provide an argument against our approach to

⁶⁸ Ibid, p. 4, refers to this case as the first one where the horizontal direct effect of a Treaty provision, addressed to Member States, is acknowledged for private relationships.

⁶⁹ Case C-43/75, para. 40.

⁷⁰ In this regard, see Alfaro (2015a), p. 4.

⁷¹ On this case law, see Sarmiento (2017), pp. 3-6.

⁷² Cherednychenko (2007), p. 202, note 10.

⁷³ Sarmiento (2007), p. 3.

⁷⁴ Ibid, p. 3.

⁷⁵ Ibid, p. 6. He examines Case C-281/98, Roman Angonese v. Cassa di Risparmio di Bolzano SpA, Judgment of 6 June 2000, ECLI:EU:C:2000:296.

⁷⁶ Ibid, p. 6.

the effect of fundamental rights stated above, but rather a line of reasoning supporting such approach.

3.4. Human Dignity in Private Relationships

The foregoing should be qualified or nuanced with regard to *human dignity* (Article 1 CFREU). Human dignity is closely linked to the inherent worth of individuals and the protection thereof, so it is shaped differently than other fundamental rights.⁷⁷ Due to its inextricable ties to the essence of human beings, human dignity cannot be limited or restricted, not even on the grounds of protecting other fundamental rights enshrined in the Charter.⁷⁸ This makes sense, since fundamental rights' ultimate purpose is to secure human dignity.⁷⁹ It follows that human dignity requires no specific legislative action for it to be relied on by individuals in private relationships, and can have an *horizontal direct effect*. This close connection with the inherent worth of individuals also explains why human dignity is inalienable, inviolable and also why it allows for no limitation or derogation, not even as an exercise of personal autonomy.⁸⁰ The CJEU case law has embraced this idea, which was largely established in *Omega*.⁸¹

The dispute arises from a ban (prohibition order) issued by German authorities on games taking place in Omega's establishment. The game involved a "laserdrome" where players had to kill other players with gun-type laser targeting devices. Players wore tags fixed on their jackets that turned them into human targets. This activity was developed by the German company Omega using children's toy guns at first and then equipment supplied by the British company Pulsar, which ended up being Omega's licensee. This case was referred for a preliminary ruling to the Court of Justice by the German Supreme Court, which was asked to assess the legality of the administrative decision imposing the aforesaid ban. The case entails a clash between the freedom to provide services and the free movement of goods, on the one hand, and respect for human dignity, on the other. The Court of Justice found that respecting human dignity falls within the public order treaty clause justifying a restriction of the abovementioned freedoms. The Court added that the contested order (which solely banned shooting at human targets) did not go beyond what is necessary to attain the objective of protecting human dignity.⁸²

If we were able to set aside the facts connected with free movement, we could easily approach the case as a conflict between the freedom to conduct a business (free enterprise) and human dignity, which would lead to a similar solution. Since human dignity overrides

⁷⁷ Alexy (1993), pp. 106-107, who points out that this fundamental right sometimes operates as a rule and some others as a principle. He adds that a distinct feature of human dignity is that there is a high degree of certainty regarding its precedence over conflicting principles within the fully protected sphere of human worth.

⁷⁸ Concerning this connection with the inherent worth of individuals, see the Opinions of AG C. Stix-Hackl, in Case C-36/02, *Omega Spielhallen- und Automatenaufstellungs-GmbH*, ECLI:EU:C:2004:162, para. 75 and AG Poiares Maduro, in Case C-303/06, *Coleman v. A. Law and S. Law*, ECLI:EU:C:2008:61, para. 9. Amongst other scholarly works, see Escarejo (2019), p. 65, including additional references. See also, Sobrino (2008), p. 108, who underlines that human dignity is absolute, non-derogable and not subject to any limitation under any other fundamental rights provided in the Charter.

⁷⁹ Alexy (1993) p. 37.

⁸⁰ Alfaro (2017), p. 9 and Sobrino (2008), see note 78 above.

⁸¹ Case C-36/02, *Omega Spielhallen- und Automatenaufstellungs-GmbH v. Oberbürgermeisterin der Bundesstadt Bonn*, Judgment of 14 October 2004, ECLI:EU:C:2004:614.

⁸² Case C-36/02, paras. 34-35.

free enterprise—keep in mind that “[h]uman dignity is inviolable” (Article 1 CFREU)—there is no need to balance the fundamental rights at stake, and there can be a restriction of free enterprise, like the one imposed by German authorities, to secure human dignity. However, note that in order for this restrictive measure to be legitimate, it must fulfil the principle of proportionality (Article 52(1) CFREU).

The foregoing has obvious direct consequences for private relationships regarding any contract provisions deemed contrary to human dignity. Contracts and contract law provide a fertile ground for the most intense conflicts between human dignity and other fundamental rights enforceable within private law relationships (see section 4 below).

3.5. The Role of the Judiciary in Fulfilling the Optimization Command

What has been discussed so far regarding fundamental rights’ distinct features and the role of legislators has an immediate impact on the role of the judiciary. Having empowered legislators to determine the “social enforceability” of fundamental rights, it is for judicial authorities to apply and interpret the provisions used by lawmakers to determine the scope of fundamental rights in private relationships.⁸³ Accordingly, the judiciary gives effect to this duty of protection imposed by fundamental rights on public authorities in the interest of fundamental right holders. Where legislators have failed to take action and fulfil their duty, judicial authorities will not be entitled to supersede them; in such cases, courts of justice are not entitled, by themselves, to strike the balance needed to enforce these rights in private relationships (relying, for instance, on general clauses of public order, good faith or morality). Judicial authorities have been removed from that task in favour of legislators, who are better suited for it.⁸⁴ Thus, courts of justice are not required to strike this balance by interpreting private law in the light of a set of fundamental rights that would permeate the whole legal order.

As for the Charter, it is for domestic judicial authorities to interpret and apply the provisions used by EU and national legislators to balance competing fundamental rights. Most certainly, regarding a national provision implementing a Directive that included such balance, courts of justice must interpret such national provision in conformity with the Directive.⁸⁵ But the role of the judiciary in fulfilling this duty of protection is not as simple as this. The Court of Justice has further specified that “[...] Member States must not only interpret their national law in a manner consistent with Community law, but also make sure they do not rely on an interpretation of wording of secondary legislation which would be in conflict with the fundamental rights protected by the Community legal order or with the other general principles of Community law.”⁸⁶ Thus, national judicial authorities must give effect to this duty of protection not only by ensuring that domestic legislators have abided by the balance between conflicting rights struck by the Directive, but also making sure that the balancing performed by the EU legislator allows to comply with the aforesaid duty of protection. Where the courts are in doubt about the compatibility of these provisions with EU secondary legislation or with the Charter, they should or they must—depending on the court hearing the case—refer a preliminary ruling

⁸³ Alfaro (1993), pp. 73 and 75, explaining that the process of interpretation leads to the “concretization” or realization of the rules for them to be applied to a specific case.

⁸⁴ Hesse (1995), p. 65.

⁸⁵ Case C-414/16, para. 79.

⁸⁶ Case C-101/01, para. 87; C-305/05, *Ordre des barreaux francophones et germanophone et al v. Conseil des ministres*, Judgment of 26 June 2007, ECLI:EU:C:2007:38, para. 28, and Case C-275/06, para. 68.

to the CJEU (Article 267 TFEU). The Court of Justice is thus called upon to act as a Constitutional Court, ensuring that legislators comply with the duty of protection.⁸⁷ Preliminary rulings will be on validity if the referring court is not sure about the compatibility with the Charter of an EU secondary law provision, and thus the ruling will determine if the EU legislator has fulfilled the duty of protection required by the fundamental rights at issue. The case *Test-Achats ASBL* aptly exemplifies this: when ruling on the question referred by the Belgian Constitutional Court, the CJEU found that Article 5(2) of Directive 2004/113 was invalid on the grounds that it was contrary to Articles 21 and 23 CFREU—prohibition of discrimination based on sex and equality between men and women.⁸⁸ Nonetheless, the Court of Justice will also be entitled to review the fulfilment of this duty of protection following an action for annulment brought under Article 263 TFEU against secondary legislation incompatible with any fundamental rights set out in the Charter.⁸⁹ Preliminary rulings will be on interpretation where the Court of Justice rules on the compatibility with EU law—including the Charter—of a national provision transposing a Directive determining the “social enforceability” of fundamental rights.⁹⁰ The Court will thus be able to establish whether the national legislator’s transposition has (i) abided by the balancing performed by the EU legislator and (ii) fulfilled the duty of protection.⁹¹ That is exactly what it did in *Mangold* and *Kücükdeveci* (see section 3.2 above). The Court of Justice notes that “it is for the national court, hearing proceedings between individuals, to ensure that the principle of non-discrimination on grounds of age, as given expression in Directive 2000/78, is complied with, disapplying if need be any contrary provision of national legislation.”⁹²

Judicial review of compliance with the duty of protection is not limited to legislators’ actions. It can also cover the activity of national courts. Indeed, within the framework of preliminary rulings on interpretation, the Court of Justice can make sure that the interpretation performed by Member State courts is not “in conflict with those fundamental rights or with the other general principles of Community law, such as the principle of proportionality.”⁹³ If the Court of Justice finds that the interpretation is incompatible with the said rights, domestic courts should cease to apply such interpretation and interpret the provision otherwise (i.e., accordingly with the EU law rules where the legislator struck the balance between the competing rights).⁹⁴

4. Fundamental Rights and Personal Autonomy

As shown above, except for human dignity, fundamental rights do not entail, by themselves, obligations on private parties. Rather, they are enforced amongst private parties through a legislative expression that determines their “social enforceability,”

⁸⁷ See the insights of Díez-Hochleitner (2013), pp. 5 and 8.

⁸⁸ Case C-236/09, *Association belge des Consommateurs Test-Achats ASBL et al v. Conseil des ministres*, Judgment of 1 March 2011, ECLI:EU:C:2011:100.

⁸⁹ For example, see C-377/98, *Kingdom of the Netherlands v. European Parliament and Council*, Judgment of 9 October 2001, ECLI:EU:C:2001:523, deciding on the application for annulment against Directive 98/44/EC, of 6 July 1998, on the legal protection of biotechnological inventions, for being contrary to human dignity (among other grounds). As for the scholarly works, Mangas (2008a), p. 820, points out this possibility.

⁹⁰ Mangas (2008b), p. 842.

⁹¹ As acknowledged, on a general basis, Mangas (2008a), p. 817.

⁹² Case C-555/07, para. 56. Along the same lines, see also Case C-144/04, para. 78.

⁹³ Case C-275/06, para. 68.

⁹⁴ Case C-414/16, paras. 72-73 and Case C-68/17, paras. 64-65.

along with the courts' interpretation and application. Fundamental rights intended to be effective within the private sphere are also covered by the aforesaid exception.

We still have to address the extent to which fundamental rights can *limit free will*. Note that personal autonomy manifests itself as the possibility of designing one's own life responsibly and in a self-determined manner.⁹⁵ Individual decisions made as an exercise of autonomy are valid inasmuch as they are wanted and accepted by the parties (*stat pro ratione, voluntas*), so that they can avail of their legal sphere as they see fit.⁹⁶ In this vein, personal autonomy must be construed as an expression of human dignity, insofar as it amounts to an essential part of the free development of personality and to the utmost expression of individual freedom.⁹⁷

This idea can be found in the Opinion of AG Poiares Maduro in *Coleman v. A. Law and S. Law*, where he provides that personal autonomy dictates that individuals "should be able to design and conduct the course of their lives through a succession of choices among different valuable options. The exercise of autonomy presupposes that people are given a range of valuable options from which to choose. When we act as autonomous agents making decisions about the way we want our life to develop our 'personal integrity and sense of dignity and self-respect are made concrete'." He adds that "a commitment to autonomy means that people must not be deprived of valuable options in areas of fundamental importance for their lives by reference to suspect classifications."⁹⁸

These insights are particularly significant regarding fundamental rights, since they lead to the conclusion that *free will cannot be limited or restricted by a general duty to respect fundamental rights*.⁹⁹ As discussed before, fundamental rights solely impose duties on public authorities (see section 2 above). Consequently, individuals should be able to define the scope of their fundamental rights through agreements, as long as such agreements do not entail a waiver of these rights. As is well-known, fundamental rights qualify as *res extra commercium* and therefore they are inalienable. As a result, any waiver of fundamental rights shall be deemed null and void, just like any waiver of the exercise of these rights being equivalent to waiving the rights altogether; for example, waiving the exercise of a fundamental right indefinitely.¹⁰⁰

Therefore, under freedom of contract, *each contracting party must protect itself through its own consent (or lack thereof) from any unbearable or unacceptable fundamental rights restrictions*. However, and here comes the problem, individual consent sometimes does not suffice to provide such protection.¹⁰¹ In these cases, in order

⁹⁵ On this approach to personal autonomy, see Hesse (1995), pp. 75-77.

⁹⁶ Alfaro (2015b), p. 1.

⁹⁷ Hesse (1995), p. 75. See Alfaro (1993), p. 94 and von Münch (1997), p. 50. More recently, Lohsse, Schulze (2016), p. 29, recall that personal autonomy is a constitutionally protected principle. In contrast, Ramos (2016), pp. 247-249, argue that personal autonomy is inextricably linked to the core or essence of fundamental rights. Based on this claim, he suggests that the potential conflicts between personal autonomy and fundamental rights should be solved by striking a fair balance and weighing the interests at stake. *Ibid*, pp. 250-264.⁹⁸ Case C-303/06, paras. 9 and 11.

⁹⁸ Case C-303/06, paras. 9 and 11.

⁹⁹ Hesse (2011), p. 172: "An unlimited connection of individuals with fundamental rights would entail a restriction of their personal autonomy, which could lead to a significant limitation of personal freedom, thereby reshaping private law's meaning and distinct nature." See also, von Münch (1997), pp. 49-50, pointing out that both fundamental rights and private autonomy "are an integral part of a democratic, liberal and social legal order subject to the rule of law."

¹⁰⁰ Alfaro (1993), pp. 99-100.

¹⁰¹ *Ibid*, p. 94.

to fulfil the duty of protection required by fundamental rights, lawmakers must take action by passing mandatory provisions that limit personal autonomy. Thus, any agreements contrary to mandatory provisions limiting personal autonomy will be null and void (see, for instance, Article 1255 of the Spanish Civil Code)¹⁰². Courts and tribunals should invalidate such agreements by applying the restrictive mandatory provision. Note, however, that judicial authorities are not entitled to add further restrictions or limitations other than those expressly laid down in the provision limiting free will.¹⁰³ Similarly, insofar as any agreements limiting fundamental rights can qualify as a waiver of rights, they should be considered null and void if they undermine human dignity (see, for instance, an enslavement agreement).¹⁰⁴ Keep in mind that, due to its very nature, human dignity has horizontal direct effect with no need for any legislative measures (see section 3.3 above). The previous case differs from those situations where the mere performance *in natura* of the agreement undermines human dignity. The agreement will be deemed valid, yet not enforceable in that way.¹⁰⁵

Based on the foregoing, individuals may exercise their freedom and refuse to enter into agreements with other individuals, unless such refusal constitutes an unlawful exercise of their freedom contrary to human dignity (Articles 1 CFREU and 7(2) of the Spanish Civil Code).¹⁰⁶ For example, the owner of a business open to the public cannot refuse the entry of persons on grounds of ethnicity or sexual orientation, because it would amount to a degrading treatment for those persons.¹⁰⁷ As has been authoritatively put, “persons who are refused entry based on their race have no chance to recover their loss of dignity resulting from such refusal by creating their ‘whatever-race-only’ association. That would not afford them the relevant status–equality–but rather it would confirm and consolidate their situation of discrimination (*‘equal but separate’*).”¹⁰⁸ In this vein, the Court considered that a practice of an electricity distributor, which imposed a different and unfavourable treatment on the inhabitants of certain ethnic group, had an “offensive and stigmatising nature”¹⁰⁹. The practice consisted in placing electricity meters on pylons at a height of seven metres in certain urban districts–whose inhabitants were in most part of Roma origin–with the purpose of avoiding unlawful connections. This made extremely difficult, or even impossible, for consumers of those districts–and only for them–to check the consumption. The Court considered that such a practice was, at least, “[...] liable to constitute an apparently neutral practice putting persons of a given ethnic origin at a particular disadvantage compared with other persons, within the meaning of Article 2(2)(b) [of Directive 2000/43]”. Since this practice inflicts a different and unfavourable treatment on a specific group based on racial grounds, it would amount to an exercise of freedom imposing an offensive and stigmatizing treatment for that group of persons. Therefore, it should be considered contrary to the (equal) human dignity–in other words, discriminatory–, unless it could be justified.¹¹⁰

¹⁰² Article 1255 of Spanish Civil Code is worded as follows: “The contracting parties may establish any covenants, clauses and conditions deemed convenient, provided that they are not contrary to the laws, to morals or to public policy”.

¹⁰³ Alfaro (1993), pp. 96-99, as well as the further elaboration on this idea in those pages.

¹⁰⁴ *Ibid.*, pp. 103-104.

¹⁰⁵ *Ibid.*, pp. 104-105.

¹⁰⁶ *Ibid.*, pp. 106-107.

¹⁰⁷ Alfaro (2015a), pp. 1-2.

¹⁰⁸ Alfaro (1993), pp. 116 and (2015b), p. 3.

¹⁰⁹ Case C-84/14, *CHEZ Razpredelenie Bulgaria AD v Komisia za zashtita ot diskriminatsia*, Judgment of 16 July 2015, ECLI:EU:C:2015:480, para. 87.

¹¹⁰ Case C-84/14, operative paragraph 4: “such a measure would be capable of being objectively justified by the intention to ensure the security of the electricity transmission network and the due recording of

A different case is the nationwide stadium ban imposed on a Bayern Munich fan recently assessed by the German Constitutional Court. This case has been considered a national example of the principle of equal treatment's horizontal direct effect.¹¹¹ However, in fact this two-year stadium ban must be construed as an exclusion to enter into agreements ("refusal to contract") where the fan's dignity is not undermined, since the ban (i) was not unreasonable or arbitrary (it was actually imposed because the fan caused personal injury and damage to property) and, as concluded by the German Constitutional Court, (ii) was reasonable or proportionate.¹¹²

5. Conclusions

Based on our findings, there are not sufficient elements to generally state that the fundamental rights enshrined in the Charter have horizontal direct effect. The CJEU case law discussed herein does not prove us wrong. The only exceptions are human dignity and fundamental rights granted or acknowledged within private law relationships.

This approach to fundamental rights' effectiveness in private relationships does not entail that the protection thereof be weaker or that fundamental rights be disregarded by a whole sphere of the legal order. Admittedly, declaring the horizontal direct effect of fundamental rights neither adds anything to their fundamental nature nor enhances the protection thereof. As shown above, their fundamental nature does not stem from their *erga omnes* effect. Rather, the fundamental nature of fundamental rights arises from the fact that their acknowledgment does not depend on legislators. Accordingly, fundamental rights are not subject to an enhanced protection solely because they are deemed effective in private relationships. Fundamental rights achieve their greatest protection where lawmakers abide by the "optimization command"—entailed by fundamental rights—and afford right holders an appropriate protection through the relevant provisions (whether private or public law, or domestic or EU provisions) subsequently interpreted and applied by judicial authorities. It is for the Court of Justice to ensure the fulfilment of this command or requirement. Where Member States breach their duties and fail to transpose the EU Directive providing the EU legislator's balance between rights at stake (or do so defectively), the Court of Justice forces domestic courts to set aside or disapply the implementing provision at issue, which is not only incompatible with the Directive, but also contrary to the fundamental right at stake. Where national law cannot be interpreted in conformity with the relevant EU Directive, national courts are not entitled to apply the Directive directly to enforce the fundamental right at hand. This evidences, however, an additional issue, that is, the lack of horizontal direct effect of Directives, which must be addressed according to a well-known case law (i.e., right of the aggrieved party to obtain

electricity consumption only if that measure did not go beyond what is appropriate and necessary to achieve those legitimate aims and the disadvantages caused were not disproportionate to the objectives thereby pursued".

¹¹¹ 1BvR3080/09. This ruling is available at: https://www.bundesverfassungsgericht.de/SharedDocs/Entscheidungen/DE/2018/04/rs20180411_1bvr308009.html. See the English translation of this ruling at https://www.bundesverfassungsgericht.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/EN/2018/04/rs20180411_1bvr308009en.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=1.

¹¹² On these matters, see Alfaro (2018), p. 1.

a reparation in accordance with national law on liability where a damage has been suffered and it is due to a breach by the State of its obligation).¹¹³

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¹¹³ Case C-91/92, Paola Faccini Dori v Recreb Srl, Judgment of 14 July 1994, ECLI:EU:C:1994:292, par. 29, and Joint Cases C-46/93 and C-48/93, Brasserie du Pêcheur SA and Federal Republic of Germany and The Queen and Secretary of State for Transport, Judgment of 5 March 1996. See also Fornasier (2015), p. 36.

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